

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Low energy electron beam to support safe whole dried insect products

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Equations used for calculating the LEEB depth-dose distribution of the dried insects

$$\text{Correction factor} = \frac{\text{density of B3 film } \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{cm}^3}\right)}{\text{density of insect } \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{cm}^3}\right)} \quad \text{equation (1)}$$

$$50\% \text{ LEEB depth} - \text{dose distribution of insects } (\mu\text{m}) = 289 \mu\text{m} \times \text{correction factor} \quad \text{equation (2)}$$

Table S1. Composition of agar media used for aerobic microbial counts.

Aerobic total viable count and bacterial spore count agar	LB agar (<i>E. coli</i>)	Yeast and moulds agar
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 15 g/L Agar; (VWR International, Belgium) • 8 g/L Nutrient Broth, (Difco, Switzerland) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 15 g/L Agar; (VWR International, Belgium) • 10 g/L Trypton (Sigma-Aldrich Switzerland) • 10 g/L NaCl (Sigma-Aldrich Switzerland) • 5 g/L Yeast extract (Sigma-Aldrich Switzerland) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 g/L Agar; (VWR International, Belgium) • 39 g/L potato dextrose agar (Sigma-Aldrich Switzerland) • 1 ml 10% lactic acid (Sigma-Aldrich Switzerland)

(a) Microwave dried BSFL

(b) Microwave dried mealworm

(c) Oven dried BSFL

(d) Oven dried mealworm

Figure S1. Surface view of the whole dried insect products used for the LEEB trials.

Table S2. Penetration depth at 50% of LEEB dose of BSFL and mealworm and the physical properties. Data displayed are mean values and standard deviation. Thickness and length sample size n=10 and density n = 2-3.

	BSFL				Mealworm			
	Density (g/cm³)	Thickness (mm)	Length (mm)	Depth (μm)	Density (g/cm³)	Thickness (mm)	Length (mm)	Depth (μm)
Microwave	0.317 ± 0.046	3.6 ± 0.5	2.0 ± 0.2	1021	0.413 ± 0.122	2.1 ± 0.4	2.2 ± 0.3	783
Oven	0.795 ± 0.023	2.3 ± 0.4	1.9 ± 0.3	407	0.604 ± 0.198	2.9 ± 0.3	2.2 ± 0.4	536

Figure S2. *E. coli* K-12 inactivation using HEEB at 10 MeV with the following doses of: 0, 1, 3, and 5 kGy and 10 kGy. The red line indicates the detection limit of 2- \log_{10} cfu/g. As a conservative approach, samples where colonies were not observed are graphed at the detection limit. Mean is shown in bold with replicates shown in grey (n=3).

Figure S3. *E. coli* K-12 numbers in the control or LEEB-treated BSFL (250 keV, 12.3 ± 2 kGy). Mean is shown in bold with replicates shown in grey (n=3). The detection limit shown in red is 2-log_{10} cfu/g dried BSFL.

Table S3. Moisture content (%) and water activity a_w (-) of microwave dried whole BSFL and mealworm. Data displayed are mean values and range (n=2).

Insect	Treatment	Physicochemical parameters	
		Moisture Content (%)	Water activity a_w
Microwave dried BSFL	Control	6.3 ± 0.05	0.40 ± 0.02
	LEEB-treated	7.2 ± 0.04	0.44 ± 0.01
Microwave dried mealworm	Control	6.1 ± 0.02	0.47 ± 0.00
	LEEB-treated	6.0 ± 0.04	0.46 ± 0.01

Table S4. Moisture content (%) and water activity a_w (-) of BSFL during six-month shelf life test. Data are displayed with mean values and standard deviation (n=3).

Treatment	Parameter	Storage time (months)						
		0	1	2	3	4	5	6
BSFL								
Control	Water activity	0.33 ± 0.05	0.37 ± 0.02	0.42 ± 0.01	0.41 ± 0.00	0.48 ± 0.00	0.48 ± 0.01	0.45 ± 0.01
		0.30 ± 0.01	0.38 ± 0.01	0.41 ± 0.01	0.41 ± 0.01	0.47 ± 0.01	0.48 ± 0.01	0.44 ± 0.00
Control	Moisture content	2.33 ± 0.01	3.0 ± 0.2	4.2 ± 0.2	4.0 ± 0.1	5.2 ± 0.1	5.5 ± 0.1	4.9 ± 0.0
		2.4 ± 0.1	3.1 ± 0.2	4.4 ± 0.1	4.3 ± 0.1	5.0 ± 0.1	5.6 ± 0.1	4.9 ± 0.1

Table S5 Moisture content (%) and water activity (-) of mealworm during six-month shelf life test. Data displayed are mean values and standard deviation (n=3).

Treatment	Parameter	Storage time (months)						
		0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Mealworm								
Control	Water activity	0.42 ± 0.01	0.46 ± 0.004	0.47 ± 0.02	0.44 ± 0.04	0.53 ± 0.01	0.53 ± 0.03	0.51 ± 0.01
	Water activity	0.41 ± 0.01	0.44 ± 0.01	0.42 ± 0.02	0.42 ± 0.04	0.49 ± 0.02	0.49 ± 0.03	0.49 ± 0.01
Control	Moisture content	6.53 ± 0.11	6.75 ± 0.06	6.72 ± 0.12	6.04 ± 0.51	7.94 ± 0.12	8.16 ± 0.12	7.09 ± 0.12
	Moisture content	6.24 ± 0.1	7.00 ± 0.13	6.73 ± 0.07	6.57 ± 0.05	8.32 ± 0.62	8.54 ± 0.05	7.29 ± 0.06

Table S6. Primary (peroxide value) and secondary (p-anisidine value) lipid oxidation were monitored during the oven-dried mealworm shelf-life at four different time points. ND: non-detect. Data displayed is of one replicate (n=1). Except for month 0 where data displayed are mean values and standard deviation (n=3).

Storage Time (months)	Treatment	Peroxide value (meq./kg fat)	p-Anisidine value (-)
0	Control	1.97 ± 0.32	N.D.
	LEEB	3.0 ± 0.1	N.D.
1	Control	1.7	0.6
	LEEB	2.8	0.6
3	Control	2.6	0.6
	LEEB	3.2	1.8
6	Control	2.3	1.8
	LEEB	3.0	1.0